

Oximidobenzotetronic Acid: A New Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt

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An ethanolic solution of oximidobenzotetronic acid reacts with an aqueous solution of cobalt to form a deep red, water-soluble complex above pH 10.0. The complex is quite stable and obeys Lambert-Beer's law at 485 m μ within the concentration range of 0 to 4.7 p.p.m. of cobalt and quantities as small as 0.02 p.p.m. of the metal can be estimated spectrophotometrically. Interference due to certain foreign ions has been studied. The most probable chelate structure, based on the evidence obtained from infrared spectrum of the compound, has been proposed.

Among many of the organic reagents reported for the colorimetric and spectrophotometric determination of cobalt, Sandell ("Colorimetric Determinations of Traces of Metals", 2nd ed., p. 271, Interscience Publishers Inc., 1950) has described and recommended nitroso-R-salt (sodium 1-nitroso-2-hydroxynaphthalene-3,6-disulphonate), *o*-nitrosophenol, and *o*-nitroresol. Thiocyanate method has been extensively used. William (*Talanta*, 1958, 1, 88) has recently surveyed the various organic reagents recommended for the colorimetric and absorptiometric determination of cobalt. Some new reagents that have been more recently suggested are : isonitroso (oximino) dimedone (Bassche and Hoste, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 18, 564), quinolinedione dioxime (Golovovina *et al.*, *Vestn. Moskov. Univ.*, 1957, 5, 187), pyridine thiocyanate (Forsythe *et al.*, *Talanta*, 1959, 1, 249), *N*-oximinoacetyl anthranilic acid (Buscaróns and Munné, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 19, 432), sodium γ -(mercaptoacetamido)benzene sulphonate (Gupta and Sogani, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 918), *NN'*-ethylenedi-(4-methoxy-1,2-benzoquinone-1-oximino-2-imine) (Mashima, *J. Chem. Soc. Japan, Pure Chem. Sect.*, 1959, 80, 1263), nicotinamidoxime (Tripathi and Banerjee, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1959, 188, 407), and dithio-oxamide (Jacobs and Yoe, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1959, 20, 332). There are various disadvantages in the use of the above reagents as many cations and anions cause interference and in most cases organic solvents are needed either to keep the complex in solution or for its extraction.

We have found that oximidobenzotetronic acid can be successfully employed for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt. The reagent has already been used by Bhat and Jain (unpublished) for the spectrophotometric determination of Fe³⁺. When a freshly prepared ethanolic solution of oximidobenzotetronic acid is added to an aqueous solution of cobalt, a brownish red suspension is produced, which dissolves completely in excess of alkali to form a deep red complex instantaneously. This reaction has been utilised for the estimation of cobalt in quantities as small as 0.02 p.p.m. of the metal in solution. The red complex so produced is water-soluble and is not extractable by organic solvents like benzene, chloroform, ether, and pentanol¹. The complex is quite stable for more than a week and the optical density of the complex is unaffected at the temperature range of 5° to 50°. The colour intensity is maximum and remains unchanged above pH 10.0. The

complex obeys Lambert-Beer's law at 485 m μ within the concentration range of 0 to 4.7 p.p.m. of cobalt. The estimation of cobalt with this reagent can be carried out even in presence of large amounts of the usually interfering foreign ions.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Hydroxycoumarin was prepared by the method of Stahman *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 2285) and readily converted into oximidobenzotetronic acid by nitrous acid as described by Anschütz *et al.* (*Annalen*, 1909, **367**, 169). Ethanolic solutions of the reagent were used.

CoSO₄·7H₂O (A. R.-B.D.H) was used for making standard solutions of cobalt. The stock solution was 2.01×10^{-3} M and 10 c.c. of it on dilution to 500 c. c. had a concentration of 4.7 p.p.m. of cobalt. All other reagents employed were of either A. R. (B.D.H) or *Pro Analyti* (Merck) quality.

A Unicam spectrophotometer, model SP 600, was used for all spectrophotometric studies. The thickness of the absorption cells used was 10 mm. All pH measurements were taken on a Beckman pH meter, model H2.

The ultraviolet absorption spectrum of oximidobenzotetronic acid has already been reported. (Bhat and Jain, *loc. cit.*). The absorption spectra of cobalt-oximidobenzotetronic acid was taken at various dilutions of cobalt between the pH range 10.0 and 12.5. The complex exhibited maximum absorption at 485 m μ as shown in Fig. 1. The

FIG. 1
A: 4.70 ppm Co. B: 1.88 ppm Co. C: 0.94 ppm Co.

absorption due to the reagent at this wave length was negligible, and hence 485 m μ was chosen for all subsequent spectrophotometric studies of the red cobalt complex. A yellow complex formed between pH 1.5 and 6.5 did not show any maximum absorption at 400-700 m μ .

Minimum Amount of Oximidobenzotetronic Acid necessary for the Estimation of Cobalt.—For this study equimolar solutions of cobalt sulphate and oximidobenzotetronic acid were made. The optical densities at 485 m μ of a series of the above solutions containing oximidobenzotetronic acid and cobalt in the molar ratios of 1:1 to 10:1 were determined. The results are plotted in Fig. 2, where it is seen that the portion AB of the curve is a straight line up to the molar ratio of 4.5. For estimation of cobalt, the molar ratio of the reagent to cobalt was, however, maintained at 10 in the subsequent studies.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Effect of pH on the Optical Density of Cobalt-oximidobenzotetronic Acid Complex.—The stock solution of the complex was 4.02×10^{-3} M with respect to cobalt. An aliquot (10 c.c.) of this solution was taken in a 25 c.c. measuring flask and the volume made to the mark using NaOH and HCl to bring the resultant solution to a pH value within 8.0 and 12.5. It was found that the absorption by the complex was maximum and unchanged above pH 10.0, as seen from Table I.

TABLE I

pH	8.0	8.7	9.0	9.4	10.0	10.8	11.3	12.0	12.5
O.D.	0.305	0.4	0.540	0.600	0.755	0.758	0.755	0.755	0.760

Between pH 7.0 and 8.0, the colour of the complex is yellowish red; below pH 7, it is yellow and a turbidity appears after about 10 minutes.

Stability of the Colour of the Complex.—The colour of the complex was found to be stable and no change in the optical density could be observed even after keeping the complex for one week. The effect of temperature on the optical density of the complex was also studied and no change in optical density was observed between 5° and 50°.

Lambert-Beer's Law.—The complex was found to obey Lambert-Beer's law between the concentration range of 0 to 4.7 p.p.m. at 485 m μ between pH 10.0 and 12.5. Under these conditions quantities as low as 0.02 p.p.m. of cobalt can be estimated, Fig. 3 shows the calibration curve,

Interference due to Foreign Ions.—The stock solution of the complex was $4.02 \times 10^{-5} M$ with respect to cobalt, having a mole ratio of the reagent to cobalt as 10. An aliquot (10 c.c.) of this solution was transferred to a 25 c.c. standard flask and mixed with a known amount of a foreign salt; the volume was made to 25 c.c. with water. The *pH* of the complex, however, was always maintained above 10.0. The concentration of the foreign salt in the complex was progressively increased till the optical density changed by 2% of the theoretical value. It was found that the anions borate, citrate, oxalate, phosphate, tartrate, fluoride, chloride, bromide, iodide, and sulphate did not interfere even if present in very large quantities. The concentrations of the following ions, which did not cause any interference, are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Cations.	Taken as.	p. p. m. tolerated.
Aluminium	Aluminate	500
Beryllium	Beryllium sulphate (in presence of citrate ions)	800
Chromium	Chromate	250
Copper	Copper sulphate	36
Molybdenum	Ammonium molybdate	1,840
Manganese	Manganese sulphate (in presence of citrate ions)	800
Nickel	Nickel sulphate (in presence of citrate ions)	600
Tungsten	Sodium tungstate	2,400
Vanadium	Ammonium vanadate	240
Zinc	Zincate	552

Acetate ions did not interfere when present at a concentration of 800 p.p.m. for 1.8 p.p.m. of cobalt. Iron (II and III) interfered in the above estimation as the reagent formed a blue complex with iron.

Recommended Procedure for Cobalt Estimation

The given cobalt solution containing 0.02 to 4.0 p.p.m. of cobalt is treated with a fresh solution containing 10 times the reagent in minimum ethanol between the temperature range of 5° and 50° . This results in the formation of a brownish red suspension. A 4% NaOH solution is then slowly added to the suspension till it dissolves completely with instantaneous formation of a deeply coloured red cobalt complex. The resultant solution is then diluted with water to a known volume and its optical density, determined at 485 μ , is measured. The concentration of cobalt is then deduced from the standard calibration curve obtained under identical conditions.

FIG. 4

Structure of Oximidobenzotetronic Acid

Anschütz (*loc. cit.*) gave structure (I) for oximidobenzotetronic acid. Taking chelation into account there are two possibilities (II and III) for the final structure. In order to decide between these two, a study of the infrared spectrum of the compound (Fig. 4) has been made. In potassium bromide pellet, the spectrum shows two absorption peaks at 1740 cm^{-1} and 1615 cm^{-1} , which could be attributed to carbonyl frequencies. This agrees very well with the requirements of formula (II), the ester carbonyl corresponding to 1740 cm^{-1} and the chelated carbonyl corresponding to 1615 cm^{-1} , although the alternative (III) could be expected to show the ester frequency much lower (1710 cm^{-1}) and the ketonic frequency much higher (1660 cm^{-1}).

(I)

(II)

(III)

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